

APPRAISAL OF PRE-SERVICE MATHEMATICS AND CHEMISTRY (MAC) TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF KNOWLEDGE AND UNDERSTANDING OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

In recent time, mathematics and chemistry (MAC) were notable disciplines for discussing climate change and its effects on planet Earth. Mathematics and chemistry (MAC) were tremendous in fostering skills of pre-service teachers' (PST) knowledge and understanding (KAU) of their physical environment and perspectives of the changes in our World. This was about applying curricula and study materials in MAC for pre-service teachers' (PST) knowledge and understanding to the constantly changing climate. This research investigated the perceptions that pre-service MAC teachers held about their KAU of climate change. The pre-service MAC teachers of COSED in LASUED formed the population for this study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design & methodology, which involved a sample of 248 PST that were selected using simple random sampling technique. The sample consisted of PST drawn from four departments that offered MAC in COSED. The only instrument (PTPCCQ) used in the study was a 26 item questionnaire, which was developed and structured by the researchers. The questionnaire had items enquiring into the perceptivity of the respondents about climate change. Frequency counts, percentages and bar charts were used to answer research questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to take decisions on the statements obtained from the open-ended part of PTPCCQ. Findings revealed that the respondents had significant perceptions of the KAU of climate change. Gender difference was found to be insignificant to the KAU of climate change. The study recommended that climate science should be introduced into the core curriculum for minimum academic standard (CCMAS) for PST's MAC programmes, as this would assist PST with better KAU of climate change. Basically, climate change models, should be incorporated into CCMAS of MAC, as that would be critical to the KAU of the reciprocal interactions between Earth's environment, atmosphere, air quality and other forces in climate change.

Index Terms - Air Pollution, Atmosphere, Climate Change, Equations, Fundamental Laws and Principles, Greenhouse Gases (GHG), Mathematics and Chemistry (MAC), Natural Gases, Pre-Service Teachers (PST).

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is phenomena attached to experiences of shifts in weather pattern. The occurrences in climate change were generally attributed to emission of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases such as Carbon (IV) Oxide – CO₂, Carbon (II) Oxide – CO, Methane – CH₄, Nitrogen (IV) Oxide – NO₂, Isooctane – C₈H₈ and many more were derived from burning fossil fuel, deforestation, cattle ranching etc. Mathematics and Chemistry (MAC) are very important disciplines in science that would be of tremendous benefit to the understanding of climate change. Importantly, mathematics is a creation of human mind and the subject deals primarily with ideas, processes, and reasoning of solving problems. In this circumstance, mathematics is of great need in the analysis and prediction of the probabilities, and in quantifying the reliabilities of climate change. Braimoh (2002) pointed out that chemistry is about human daily living and human activities, so it functions as a real-life science subject. Chemistry helped in understanding, monitoring, protecting and improving the environment around us. The knowledge of Chemistry had been useful in understanding the process and effects of climate change on planet Earth. Chemistry had been applicable to determining and understanding how climate change would affect the present state and the future of planet Earth. So, atmospheric chemistry, as a branch of chemistry was dedicated to involve learning about chemical processes going on in the Earth, especially as they affect the quality of air, water and soil found in the atmosphere.

Mathematics is not just a subject but a language of science and technology, which had been in use over the years to solve various real-life problems, be it in industries, economy, engineering, science, technology, geography and education. As rightly noted by Adewale, Odumosu and Olusesan (2017), mathematics had been a very big servant to humanity. Significantly, physical, biological, and economical phenomena could be communicated through mathematics. The use of the concepts like shape, size, mathematical equations, models and fundamental laws were few of concepts that were of great use to human's everyday activities. There existed a wide range of other applications of mathematics, in different areas of human endeavours, notably, mathematics was involved in the design and structure of World's ancient wonders, such as the great pyramids of Egypt, the great wall of China, the hanging gardens of Babylon, the Tam Mahal of Agra, and several others (Odumosu and Eguntola; 2010). Mathematics had been there for reasoning, critical and logical thinking for finding solutions to the challenges against humanity and human existence.

In all of the statements above, Mathematics was found to be of important use in the processing of data and modelling of information obtained during instances of global warming and soil contamination. The mathematical models and equations developed for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) were used to assess the Industrial Product and Process Use (IPPU), in the course of enforcing standards for greenhouse gases emission and carbon emission by companies and other establishments. Mathematics had been used in climate change to explain the proportions of greenhouse gases (GHG) and carbon emission in the atmosphere and quantifying the biodiversity of gases in environments. If global warming led to depreciation of ice cores

in arctic region, mathematics would be used to calculate the rate of depreciation of the ice cores. The information from such situation could be used to prevent high sea rises and flooding. Mathematical equations were also used in General Circulation Models (GCMs) to calculate the amount of energy and matter in various parts of land and in oceans. Importantly, mathematics is essential for communicating environmental data in climate change.

As earlier mentioned, chemistry is a branch of science, and essentially a part of general education embedded with knowledge and skills for improving human life and sustainability. Chemistry involved learning about our environment and the happenings around us. Climate change is an example of the happenings, which were organised as concepts in atmospheric chemistry. Rap, Geller, Katchevich, Gbarin and Blonder (2023) observed the consequences and challenges in the increase of emission of greenhouse gases (GHG), and increase in the atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases (such as CO₂, NO₂, N₂O, CH₄, SO₂, CFCs). They equally explained how the (GHG) gases have affected the atmosphere, troposphere, and stratosphere. The injurious effects and consequences of the GHG were responsible for climate change. Essentially, chemistry had been studying the processes and effects of climate change on planet Earth, and finding solutions to the unusual balance of nature. Greenhouse gases (GHGs) are pollutants and some other pollutants in the GHG group (such as SO₂ and NO) in high concentration could form acid rain, which pollutes soil and water and damage buildings (Di Napoli and McGushin, 2022).

Climate change could as well be caused by the depletion of the Ozone (O₃) layer. The O₃ layer helps in preventing injurious Sun's ultraviolet rays from getting into the Earth. Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) are the major solvents that depletes Ozone-layer (O₃) layer. Other Ozone-layer (O₃) thinning substances are Halon, Methyl Chloroform (CH₃CCl₃), Carbon Tetra Chloride (CCl₄), Hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), Halocarbon refrigerants and Methyl bromides. These harmful substances were introduced into the atmosphere by industries, by burning fossil fuels, by use of harmful chemicals, and by spraying aerosols and pesticides. These gases remove the shield of O₃ layer and cause harsh weather patterns and extremely high temperature, which in overtime led to damage in farming products, contaminating soil, causing skin cancer and eye cataracts.

Chemistry plays an important role in determining the current state and the predictions of the future states of Earth's climate. That is the meeting point for mathematics and chemistry, since mathematics would be used to calculate the period of time and extent of havoc or damage to be experienced by any foreseen Earth's climate change, chemical processes in the atmosphere would determine the abundances and properties of atmospheric forcing agents that would be chemically active during the predicted period of climate change. The overwhelming weight of scientific evidences showed that human activities were predominantly responsible for climate change (Di Napoli and McGushin, 2022). Some observable human activities adduced to causing climate change included the increase in carbon (IV) oxide (CO₂) and carbon (II) oxide (CO) emitted from burning of fossil fuel and automobiles, the issue of industrial revolution, depletion of Ozone (O₃) and global warming. Human understanding of climate change, both collectively and

individually, would continue to involve the importance of mathematics and be critical to the reflective knowledge of chemistry.

Ravishankara, Yinon and John (2015) observed that human activities had affected our environment and deteriorated its quality. Upon that Braimoh (2002) reported that the major donors to the foreseen human caused climate change would have aroused from carbon (IV) oxide (CO₂) and carbon (II) oxide (CO) that were generated by the burning of fossil fuels, and the greenhouse gases (GHG) generated domestically and by industries. The increase in greenhouse gases (GHG) concentration and pollution (air, water and soil) had influenced climate change on planet Earth.

2. STATEMENTS OF THE PROBLEM

The 2022 annual report of the United Nation Environment Programme (UNEP) as published in 2023 revealed how the 50th anniversary of the body “adopted landmark agreements to curb pollution, protect and revive biodiversity, and support nations most vulnerable and impacted by climate change... (UNEP, 2023).” The decimating impact of climate change as explained by the report had been responsible for the increased food and energy prices across the World. The position of the 50th assembly of UNEP had accomplished the fact that climate change is the most urgent problem of planet Earth.

Climate change could involve experiences that threaten people’s livelihoods and community havocs. It was established from literature that climate change could be associated with challenges that caused intense heat waves, melting glacier, rising sea levels, storms and warming oceans, and flooding (Short and Neckles, 1999; Ravishankara, Yinon and John 2015). Nigeria could particularly be vulnerable to climate change, because of the large volume of heat generated from burning fossil fuels, power generation (domestic and industrial), and emission of greenhouse gases (GHG), which had resulted into flooding, heat waves, drought and threats to food security (Ahmed, 2020).

The much dependence on rain water for agriculture and domestic usage in Nigeria were necessitated by the high levels of poverty and low level of human and physical capital, and justified by the shortage of food and energy supply in the country. UNEP (2023) informed that the increase in prices of food and cost of energy were the consequences of such situations. Of course, Nigeria’s vulnerability to the impact of climate change was from the country’s much dependency on natural resources. Desertification was experienced in the Northern part of Nigeria due to the impacts of climate change. The Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) reported the food insecurity in Nigeria (Mojeed, 2023). According to Mojeed (2023), the food insecurity crisis in Nigeria left 25million in acute hunger. Further to that, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) has declared state of emergency in the agricultural sector. The traceable consequences of climate change in Nigeria had been extreme weather conditions, lack of potable water, storms, rise in atmospheric temperature, sea level rises, poor health conditions and scarcity of food. In developing the statements of problem for this study, the researchers searched into the character and magnitude of the vulnerability effects of climate change in Nigeria,

thus investigated the criterion in the perceptions of pre-service MAC teachers about their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change.

3. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the perceptions of pre-service chemistry and mathematics (MAC) teachers' knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change in Nigeria. Notably, there were many consequences and challenges associated with climate change and the researchers examined the perceptiveness of pre-service MAC teachers' about their KAU of climate change and investigated into the factors that enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. Specifically, the study aimed at finding:

- a. How pre pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers perceive their knowledge and understanding of climate change
- b. How pre-service male and female MAC teachers' perceive their knowledge and understanding of climate change.
- c. How pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers of different programmes/course of studies perceive their knowledge and understanding of climate change.
- d. How pre-service MAC teachers perceive the factors, which enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding of climate change.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What perceptions do pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers hold about their knowledge and understanding of climate change?
2. What perceptions do pre-service male and female MAC teachers hold about their knowledge and understanding of climate change?
3. How do pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers of different programmes/courses of studies perceive their knowledge and understanding of climate change?
4. What perceptions do pre-service MAC teachers' hold about the factors that enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding of climate change?

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was a descriptive survey type. The population focused on entire pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers in the College of Science Education (COSED), Lagos State University of Education (LASUED). 248 pre-service MAC teachers were selected for the study with use of simple random sampling technique. There were 94 male and 154 female pre-service MAC teachers that voluntarily participated and selected for the research. Data were collected to describe the perceptions of the pre-

service teachers (PST) about their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. The 26 item instrument employed for the survey was the *Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of Climate Change Questionnaires (PTPCCQ)*. The instrument was developed and structured by the researchers. The PTPCCQ had questions on the perceptions, which respondents held about their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change.

The first part (Section A) of PTPCCQ consisted of the respondents' personal information/characters such as name of college, age, gender and programme of study. The section B contained 19 items of statements, which solicited responses from the respondents on a four-point scale. Rating for perceptions in section B, were coded as *strongly agree (4)*, *agree (3)*, *disagree (2)*, and *strongly disagree (1)*. There were seven (7) open ended questions in section C of PTPCCQ. The open ended questions required short answers and were made to elicit opinions from the participants on issues relating to the perceptions held for their knowledge and understanding of climate change. The statements obtained in section C were organised into themes, coded and categorised using SPSS 24. PTPCCQ was face validated by two (2) experts in mathematics education, two (2) experts in chemistry education and two (2) experts in geography. The 26 items formed a coherent scale and demonstrated good internal consistency and reliability (Cronbach alpha = 0.83). The research questions were answered using frequency counts, percentages, and bar charts, while further analyses for decisions in the open ended questions were formed by organising the statements into themes, categorising the themes and coding them. Data obtained were analysed with the *Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)* at 0.05% significant levels.

6. RESULTS

Research Question 1: What perceptions do pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers hold about their knowledge and understanding of climate change?

The results for research question 1:

Figure 1: Perceptions of pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers about their knowledge and understanding of climate change

The bar-chart in Figure 1 showed that 50.71% of the pre-service MAC teachers possessed the knowledge and understanding of MAC that would be used to analyse climate change. 56.15% of the respondents revealed that they held perceptions for chemical reactions in the knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. It was reported in the survey that 47.18% of the pre-service teachers (PST) perceived that mathematical models could be used for calculating the effects of climate change. The pre-service MAC teachers expressed perceptivity of 46.67%, 52.32% and 58.17% respectively for calculations of per cent of greenhouse gases (GHG) in chemical pollution, calculations of chemical emission and calculations of chemical biodiversity of gases, with their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change.

Many of the respondents (50.6%) perceived that their ability to calculate and analyse resource consumption would support their KAU of climate change. A majority of the PST agreed that adequate knowledge and understanding of mathematics would be helpful in solving problems of climate change, such as, in finding the presence of heavy metals in soil and soil fertility (67.44%). Perceptivity of the participants for using knowledge and understanding of mathematics in calculating volume of gases in air pollution was obtained as 67.54%. A large number of the respondents (69.86%) also agreed that chemical models and use of algorithm would be helpful in predicting how climate change would affect the future. The study reported that 42.04% of the respondents perceived mathematics and chemistry (MAC) to be helpful for predicting climate change in the future, while 64.52% of the PST perceived that concepts in mathematical modelling, differential equation and Socratic methods had potentials for generic ideas towards predicting future climate change. Finally, from results, the participants revealed with 58.79% perceptivity that mathematical laws and principles, measurements, use of calculus and statistical tools would be helpful in determining chemical contents of substances that influenced climate change.

Research Question 2:

What perceptions do pre-service male and female MAC teachers hold about their knowledge and understanding of climate change?

Figure 2: Perceptions of pre-service male and female mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers of their knowledge and understanding of climate change

The bar-chart in Figure 2 showed that 54.46% of the pre-service male mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers held perceptions that mathematics and chemistry would help them in their knowledge and understanding of climate change. In the same perspective, 55.19% of the female was of the perceptivity that mathematics and chemistry (MAC) would support their knowledge and understanding of climate change.

Research Question 3:

How do pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers of different programmes/course of studies perceive their knowledge and understanding of climate change?

Figure 3: Perceptions of pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers of different programmes/course of studies and their knowledge and understanding of climate change

The bar-chart in Figure 3 showed that some of the respondents did not perceive that their programmes/courses would provide them with knowledge and understanding of climate change. The pre-service teachers (PST) in that category included computer science (CSC SC) - PST, physics education (PHY ED) – PST, and physics science (PHY SC) -PST. It was revealed that the biology education (BIO ED) perceptivity for the knowledge and understanding of climate change was 53.61%. The pre-service biology science (BIO SC) teachers' perceptions were recorded as 54.68%. The chemistry education (CHE ED) pre-service teachers' perceptions gave 55.98%, while that of chemistry science (CHE SC) was very high at 68.67%. The study recorded 57.80% as the perceptions of pre-service computer education (CSC ED) teachers. The pre-service integrated science education (ITS ED) teachers held perceptions of 54.81% to show that their course of study would influence their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. The mathematics education (MTH ED) pre-service teachers had 52.88% perceptions for the KAU of climate change, while mathematics science (MTH SC) recorded 51.64% perceptions for the same purpose. The results also revealed that statistics education (STA ED) pre-service teachers perceived with 53.85% that their programmes would influence their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate, and statistics science (STA SC) pre-service teachers' perceptivity for PST on climate change was obtained as 56.49%.

7. ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

Data were further analysed to probe into the pre-service MAC teachers' perceptions of the factors that will enhance and limit their understanding and knowledge of climate change, which invariably answered research question 4 and helped in identifying the problems of the pre-service MAC teachers in their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of the challenges and consequences of climate change.

The pre-service teachers' perceptions of climate change questionnaires (PTPCCQ), which was the only instrument in this survey, had seven (7) open ended questions in its section C. The open ended questions required short answers and were made to elicit opinions from the respondents on issues relating to the perceptions, which they held about their knowledge and understanding of climate change. The statements made by the respondents for the open-ended questions were organised into themes, coded and categorised using SPSS 24. Data obtained were further analysed with the *Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)* at 0.05% significant levels.

Table 1: Perceptions of pre-service Mathematics and Chemistry (MAC) teachers of factors that enhance and limit their understanding and knowledge of climate change

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1068.638	9	118.738	6.992	.050
Within Groups	4041.733	238	16.982		
Total	5110.371	247			

The outcome [$F(9, 238) = 6.99; p = 0.05$] in table 1, showed that the pre-service mathematics and chemistry teachers did not significantly differ in their perceptions of the factors that enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding of climate change. This result was supported by the outcome in Figure 3, which showed that pre-service chemistry science (CHE SC) teachers held very high perceptivity of 68.67%. Figure 3 also reveal that chemistry education PST held perceptions of 57.6%.

The Scheffe Post-hoc test for the results in Figure 3 showed that the high per cent of the perceptions of pre-service chemistry science (CHE SC) teachers, were derived from their pre-knowledge and understanding of some properties of climate change.

Chemistry had concepts that discussed the properties of air, water, soil and atmosphere, and how they were impacted by climate change. Indifferences (0) in perceptions were recorded for three programmes/courses in Figure 3, i.e. in CSC.SC, PHY.ED & PHY.SC. As separated from the three programmes/courses mentioned, the per cent of the participants for their perceptions about climate change, in all programmes/courses on Figure 3 were obtained to be above 52%. Basically, the pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers did not significantly differ in their perceptions of the factors that enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change.

Table 2: Perceptions of pre-service male and female MAC teachers of factors that enhance and limit their understanding and knowledge of climate change

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	47.452	1	47.452	2.306	0.05
Within Groups	5062.919	246	20.581		
Total	5110.371	247			

The result in table 2 [$F(1,246) = 2.306$; $p = 0.05$] showed that the pre-service male and female did not differ significantly in their perception of factors that enhance and limit their knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. The outcome reported in Figure 2 revealed that the male and female students held same perceptions for factors that enhance and limit their KAU of climate change. The decision obtained from the analyses on Table 2 was found to align with that of Figure 2, which informed that 54.46% of the male PST and 55.19% of the female PST held insignificantly different perceptions of climate change. Results in the findings revealed that mathematics and chemistry (MAC) concepts would help pre-service teachers in their knowledge and understanding of climate change.

8. DISCUSSION

Findings in this study revealed that mathematics and chemistry (MAC) could be used to provide the required knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change. By and large, the study had particularly created eye opening revelations, which showed that MAC concepts did influenced the knowledge and understanding of climate change (Cardetti and LeMay, 2019; Adewale, Odumosu and Olusesan 2017). Aspects of organic, inorganic and atmospheric chemistry had provided panacea to traceable consequences of climate change such as extreme weather conditions, storms, rise in atmospheric temperature, global warming and other chemical processes that affected quality air, water, soil and the atmosphere (Ahmed, 2020; Heshmenti, 2020; Braimoh, 2002). Mathematics and chemistry (MAC) in climate change were focused on protection of the atmosphere, ozone (O₃) layer, human life and its sustainability (Mojeed, 2023; Odumosu and Eguntola, 2010). This led to the mitigation and adaptation strategies in human intervention efforts, commonly termed as “geo-engineering” or “solar radiation management” in environmental studies. The recommendations for renewable and biodegradable materials in green chemistry were proven ways of getting closer to nature and having clean atmosphere. The results evidently provided by pre-service mathematics and chemistry (MAC) teachers in this study had created strategic pathways in building a sustainable future for improved human health, clean atmosphere and environment that would be relatively free from injurious climate in Nigeria.

It was further revealed in the study that mathematics and chemistry (MAC) concepts were considerably used for analysing climate change as supported by literature (Cardetti and LeMay, 2019; Adewale, Odumosu and Olusesan 2017). Further, majority of the respondents gave evidences that would aid the understanding, analysing and solving problems relating to climate changes.

The findings revealed that the knowledge and understanding of mathematics and chemistry did influenced climate change and would help in the analysis of the processes and effects of issues relating to climate change. This could be linked to the work of Barwell (2013), when he narrated that the role of learners in mathematics education is crucial in the understanding of the climate situation in their (learners') communities.

Summarily, this research showed that mathematics and chemistry (MAC) would be useful in communicating climate change to policy makers, school administrators, curriculum experts and officials of relevant government agencies. MAC would as well be helpful in predicting, analysing and communicating climate change. The information obtained in the process of communicating climate change may be in form of text, charts, structures, equations, tables, graphs, reactions, graphics or diagrams. A good understanding of the communicating concepts in MAC would be useful for the knowledge and understanding of climate change. Of note, was the fact, as established, in that climate change had been involved in different aspects of human life. Climate change could also be linked with concepts in agriculture, biology, biodiversity, geology, geography, medicine, engineering and construction, insurance and education. In all of those disciplines, the knowledge and understanding of climate change would be required, while MAC concepts would block the gaps between other disciplines/course of studies and climate change. MAC was a combination of ideas and principles that helped in the knowledge and understanding of climate change.

9. CONCLUSION

The degree of literacy in mathematics and chemistry (MAC) was basically required for use and interpretation of data, graphs, chemical reactions, equations and analysis. As earlier mentioned, these attributes of MAC were also involved in the knowledge and understanding of climate change. Meanwhile, efforts should be intensified in the core curriculum for minimum academic standard (CCMAS) for degree programmes/courses, so that the mathematics and chemistry concepts involved, could be able to address contemporary societal climate challenges and further strengthen the positive transformations in climate change. MAC departments in colleges should be able to develop climate change models that would be useful to immediate academic communities for understanding reasons for climate to respond to different environmental factors, like biophysical conditions of land, water, soil and/or the physical and chemical processes of the atmosphere. This study also proved that climate change models in mathematics concepts would be essential for predicting future climate conditions and for studying the movements of planets.

In recent times, the global response to climate change has been impressive. It is of great relief that the growing interest and participation from all stakeholders in the ecosystem and the efforts to share more messages about climate change globally is increasing and beneficiary. Hence, countries, governments, institutions, organisations, and individuals all over the world have put different and significant efforts to mitigate climate impacts. The mitigation of climate impacts had been yielding positive effects.

The UN-backed scientific assessment panel on Ozone (O₃) depleting substances (2023), in the latest quadrennial assessment report of 2022, as published in January 9, 2023, confirmed that there had been a notable recovery of the ozone layer in the upper stratosphere and decreased human exposure to harmful ultraviolet rays from the sun, the report added that if current global policies, practices and efforts remain in place, the ozone (O₃) layer is expected to be recover back, before 2066. To reap these efforts quickly, knowledge of mathematics and chemistry (MAC) is a must. Sure, adequate knowledge of MAC has a great role to play and thorough understanding of MAC would largely help in the knowledge and understanding of climate change. Furthermore, efforts of the adequate knowledge of mathematics and chemistry in climate change awareness and sensitisation will further strengthen the positive changes recorded so far.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were deduced from the analyses and findings:

- Climate science should be embedded in the core curriculum for minimum academic standard (CCMAS) in Bachelors' degree course-contents for mathematics and chemistry, and be taught as a compulsory or general course to all pre-service teachers (PST) in Nigerian universities. Such development would help PST in understanding of how climate change affects air, water, soil, natural resources and food production.
- It was recommended that future research should emphasise more about the understanding of the consequences and challenges of climate change.
- It was recommended that departments of mathematics and chemistry in colleges should develop and regularly use climate analysis software tools for ease prediction of climate change and possible preparation for the consequences and challenges of climate change.
- Climatologists were advised on the need to pay attention to the importance of mathematics and chemistry concepts that would help in the knowledge and understanding of climate change.
- It would be advised for Nigerian government to influence and sponsor more researches and studies on climate change education, so as to contribute effectively to the contemporary volumes of published works on climate change education in Africa.
- The researchers recommended that there should be concerted efforts to excite all stakeholders in the ecosystem to become more interested and to arouse participation in the publicity and sharing of more messages about climate change across the World.
- Mathematics and chemistry (MAC) departments in colleges should be encouraged to develop climate change models that would be useful to immediate academic communities for understanding reasons for climate to respond to different

environmental factors, like biophysical conditions of land and water, and/or the physical and chemical processes of the atmosphere.

- It was recommended that Global agencies on climate change should spread across Africa and intensify efforts towards militating against the threats of climate change, so as to ensure security for the sustenance of planet Earth and its immediate environment.
- The Federal Ministry of Environment and the academic communities in Nigeria should be charged with responsibilities to evaluate the “*Human Rights Frameworks for Climate Change*”, and develop useful documents, which would guide the formulation of the “*Nigeria Climate Change Policy*,” which would help against future threats and challenges of climate change.
- It was recommended that future studies on the appraisal of pre-service mathematics and chemistry teachers’ perception about knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change should be extended to other African countries, so as to have further contributions to the literature on the knowledge and understanding (KAU) of climate change.

11. End Section

11.1 Appendices

Appendix A: Authors Contributions

¹Odumosu, M. O. and ²Odumosu, O. J. – Made substantial contributions to the conceptualisation, design and methodology for this research.

¹Odumosu, M. O. and ³Olaleye, B. O. –Engaged in data collection, formal analysis, interpretation of data and accurate representation of data.

⁴Braimoh, D. S. –Committed to drafting the work, reviewing, and revising it critically for important intellectual contents.

All four authors have ensured the originality, integrity and accurate account/report of this study, thus gave consent to the final approval and agreement for publishing this manuscript.

All four researchers contributed and sponsored all expenses incurred in carrying out the research, data collection and processing, and for developing of the report. The authors paid for all expenses in publishing the report.

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